

Table S2. Number and category of associated SNPs.

Category	Body	Crown	Cheek	Elevation
Associated SNPs	999	501	77	7
Genes within 10Kbp	637	153	45	5
Missense variants	9	1	0	0
3'/5' UTR	55	14	2	0
Up/downstream	226	87	7	1
Intron variants	822	274	44	6
Synonymous variants	9	3	0	0